

NCAS Capel Dewi
Atmospheric Observatory
<https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/>

Minutes of the 65th Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory Users' Meeting

which was held on 22nd July 2020 online owing to Covid-19 restrictions.

(This document was finalised on 19th February 2021)

Present:

(BB) Dr Barbara Brooks^{4,6}
(CJW) Dr Chris Walden^{4,5}
(DAH) Dr David Hooper^{1,4,5} Secretary
(EGN) Dr Emily Norton⁴
(GV) Prof Geraint Vaughan^{4,7} Chair
(GAP) Dr Graham Parton^{2,4,5}
(HMAR) Dr Hugo Ricketts^{4,7}
(LD) Mr Les Dean¹

Affiliation:

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMOF Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility
ISP Internet Service Provider
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
PE Public Engagement
RWP Radar Wind Profiler
SP Sam Pepler
STFC Science and Technology Facilities Council
UofM University of Manchester
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

There were no comments on the minutes of the previous meeting.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he was continuing to extend the coverage of v4 files.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that James Groves had recently given him details of how this could be achieved. However, he has not yet had time to implement it.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make available the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data in NCAS-approved files through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made no progress on this action since the last meeting.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

DAH reported that no progress had been made on making the files available. He noted that TXA is no longer reporting its status when interrogated.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this was currently a lower priority than restoring other data streams. However, he has created python software for accessing version 2 radial files, which he needs for analysing m-mode data.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

ONGOING

GAP will report on progress made in section 3a.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to arrange for installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this action was on hold owing to Covid-19 restrictions.

ACTION ITEM 64.2.1 DAH and GAP to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar available through CEDA.

ONGOING

This action currently has a low priority.

3. Observatory Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP reported that he had discussed harmonising the names of directories containing MST Radar data products, i.e. addressing action item 62.3.1, with Sam Pepler (SP) at CEDA. The issue of data being spread across directories with inconsistent names affects a number of other datasets. This is typically the result of changes to the name of an instrument. CEDA's backup system depends on the original directory names. Consequently, changing them will not be a simple issue. GAP will wait for SP to create a software tool that makes such changes easy to implement.

DAH reported that he had encountered problems with file transfers from the CDAO to the JASMIN system at the beginning of Covid-19 restrictions in late March 2020. It is not clear whether the primary cause of the problem was the broadband router at the CDAO (see section 3c) or an issue with the JASMIN platform.

The old "cron" JASMIN computer, which DAH has been relying on for automatic processes, was switched off on 10th July 2020. DAH has had to adapt his scripts to run on the replacement computer, which uses a slightly different operating system. For some reason, although the plot creation routines work when launched from the command line, they do not work when launched as automatic "cron" jobs. DAH has contacted the JASMIN helpdesk about this problem, but they have not yet been able to identify the reason for it. For the time being, daily plots will only become available once DAH has launched the scripts manually. This will typically be by mid morning of the day following data acquisition, but there will be longer delays over weekends and when DAH is on leave.

3b) Electricity - DAH

DAH noted that the electricity bill for January 2020 was approximately a third larger than the one for December 2019. He suspects that this is because the electricity usage has been estimated. The supplier thinks that the meter was last read in 2016, although LD thinks that it was done more recently. As a separate issue, NERC will be changing the provider for remotely monitoring electricity usage at its sites. Engineers working for the new provider will need to visit the CDAO in order to install new monitoring equipment (it does not appear that the old monitoring equipment was ever functional). However, Covid-19 restrictions make the timing of such a visit uncertain.

DAH reported that he had visited the CDAO on 10th and 11th March 2020 in order to allow electrical work to be carried out within the site bungalow. This required all equipment had to be powered down between 08:30 and 15:50 UTC on the 10th. New light fixtures have been installed within the main room and transmitter room and a new electrical distribution board has installed in the transmitter room. The latter is now ready for installation of the ATRAD radar equipment. Unfortunately, the planned Portable Appliance Testing could not be carried out since the person responsible was off sick on the day.

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units reported brief input power problems on 3 occasions: on 11th February, 1st March, and 21st July 2020. Although multiple problems were reported on the afternoon of 16th February 2020, this was only by 2 of the units (TX5 and Beamform).

There was a total loss of mains power at 16:15 UTC on Saturday 7th March 2020. Although DAH was able to restart the MST Radar remotely at 19:15 UTC, he did not notice that the beam steering unit was stuck in a single, off-vertical direction until the following morning. He stopped the radar briefly at around 08:40 UTC on the 8th so that he could clear the problem.

In order to prepare for the possibility that LD might not be able to visit the CDAO after Covid-19 restrictions began, new batteries were installed in the receiver room UPS unit on 20th March 2020. For some reason, the output power cut out briefly at around 07:45 UTC on Sunday 31st May 2020. The radar control and data processing computers appear to have restarted automatically afterwards. DAH

was able to restart the MST Radar remotely at 09:25 UTC.

3c) Telecommunications

There was a thunderstorm at around 01:00 UTC on 17th February 2020, which had multiple impacts. It led to failures of the broadband routers for both the NCAS and University of Manchester (UofM) networks, the telephone handset, one of the switches on the UofM network, and some “wall wart” power supply units (i.e. the type built into a plug). Although the MST Radar and Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) continued to operate, the MST Radar receiver suffered from a large drop in the sensitivity. It was replaced by the spare receiver at around 16:00 UTC on the 19th.

Internet connections on the “alarm” and “fax” lines were restored on 18th March. However, the “phone” line remained out of action until 11th March 2020, when OpenReach engineers replaced a failed capacitor within the junction box. DAH noted that having a spare internet connection on the “alarm” line had proved to be invaluable during this period. The failed Draytek router for the NCAS network was replaced by an old D-Link router on 18th February. However, it was prone to occasionally losing its connection, which required it to be manually power-cycled. Breaks of the internet connection for more than 24 hours trigger a known bug in the MST radar’s time-continuity algorithm. This led to reductions in useful altitude coverage between 12th and 17th March.

Although DAH had ordered a new Draytek router immediately after the failure of the original one, it did not arrive until a few days after he had returned from his visit to the CDAO on 12th March 2020. Owing to the fact that a reliable internet connection was going to be of vital importance once the impending Covid-19 restrictions began, DAH posted the CDAO’s original (15 year old) Speedtouch router to LD as soon as he returned from his visit. It was installed on 17th March. The new Draytek router arrived shortly afterwards and LD installed it on 20th March. Although it allowed the NCAS network to see the internet, DAH was unable to connect to the NCAS network from the outside. Consequently the Speedtouch router was reinstalled and proved to be reliable.

DAH reported that the OpenReach engineers who had visited the CDAO on 11th March thought that someone further up the Capel Dewi valley already had a fibre broadband connection. This could potentially make it easier to get “fibre on demand” to the Capel Dewi site.

ACTION ITEM 65.3.1 DAH to make enquires about the possibility of installing a fibre broadband connection to the CDAO.

NEW

3d) Miscellaneous

The fire extinguishers were tested on 7th February 2020.

The CDAO became part of the new Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF) on 1st April 2020. DAH has spent a lot of time in recent months creating CDAO content for the new AMOF website, <https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/capel-dewi-atmospheric-observatory-cdao/>. The old <http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/> website will need to remain active until DAH has had time to transfer all of the content to the AMOF website. DAH has made enquiries with the Internet Service Provider (ISP) for the CDAO to see if he can get webspace with an AMOF/NCAS branded name to replace the supplementary website, <http://www.mstrf.eclipse.co.uk/>. The sole purpose of this site is to display the latest 24 hours’ worth of data. However, the ISP no longer provides web space as part of their connection packages.

DAH attended an online talk by Hannah King from NERC’s Public Engagement (PE) team on 18th February 2020. NERC wants to shift the attitude on PE as something that is “nice to have” to something

that is essential. The key words for their latest PE strategy are “Responsibility”, “Impact”, and “Relevance”.

DAH had been accepted to give a presentation for NERC's PE Showcase event, which was due to be held in Cardiff in July 2020. NERC had specifically requested contributions that had a Welsh theme. DAH attended a training day in Cardiff on 24th February 2020. However, the showcase event was canceled owing to Covid-19 restrictions.

4. CDAO Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH had held back the NASA Ames data file for 24th May 2020 since he thought that the constant temperature during the first 7 hours of the day looked unrealistic. He suspected that the single tip recorded for the tipping bucket rain gauge at 09:20 UTC on 27th May 2020 was likely to be the result of dew accumulation (the Vaisala LD40 indicated that the sky was cloud-free throughout the day). However, he was surprised that it had occurred so long after sunrise. GAP pointed out that the British Geological Survey had detected a small earthquake at 09:04 UTC on this day and wondered if this could have been the cause of the tip.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The wind directions recorded by the data logger have remained unrealistically close to 30° ever since the power supply failed at the end of October 2019 (it was replaced on 29th November). DAH and LD visited Frongoch on 11th March 2020 in order to investigate the problem, but were unable to solve it. The feed from the wind vane was removed from the logger and reconnected. Following a suggestion from a Campbell Scientific engineer, DAH reinstalled the logger's acquisition software. A further suggestion made by Campbell Scientific was to reinstall the logger's operating system. However, DAH was not in a position to try this out at the time. BB suggested using an oscilloscope to test the voltage being generated by the wind vane. She pointed out that she has a number of Gill Instruments wind vanes and could provide one for Frongoch.

The logger's 3G communications modem lost its connection on 3 occasions: between 2nd and 6th March, 14th and 22nd May, and 7th and 21st July. In each case LD had to visit Frongoch and power-cycle the modem in order for the connection to be restored.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH reported that he had noticed occasional corrupted characters in the raw data logs during the winter of 2019/2020. He wasn't sure whether this was caused by the instrument, the connecting cable, or the logging computer. BB suggested checked for earth leakage on the instrument.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There was nothing to report on this instrument.

4e) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that all of the time-lapse videos that he has created from sky-camera images can now be accessed through the AMOF website, <https://amof.ac.uk/instruments/cdao-sky-camera/>.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

The camera is currently in action for its summer season. DAH showed an image taken at 02:00:01 UTC on 11th July 2020, which showed the comet Neowise as well as NLCs. This image has been used both by NCAS for their Twitter feed and by RAL Space for their staff newsletter. DAH has created a time-lapse video of this period, which is available from <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1483/>. He has also created a video for the night of 21st/22nd June 2020, which is available from <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1481/>.

DAH restarted the creation of MST Radar m-mode plots on 11th June 2020 and has filled the gap since they were last made available in 2015. These plots now show the radar return signal power for all 3 beam pointing directions used during the summer months. The older plots only show the signal power for the Vertical beam, even when other beam pointing directions have been used.

4g) MST Radar

At the beginning of the Covid-19 restrictions in March 2020, DAH had had to make a case for keeping the the MST Radar in operation to STFC management. This case was strengthened by the fact that E-PROFILE had highlighted the increased importance of Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) data for weather forecasting organisations. The dramatic reduction in the number of commercial aircraft in operation as a result of Covid-19 restrictions had lead to a corresponding reduction in the primary source of upper-air wind data. This impact story was covered by an NCAS press release, <https://ncas.ac.uk/forecasters-turn-to-welsh-radar-to-ease-unexpected-coronavirus-impact/>.

RAL had approved DAH's request for LD to be classified as an "essential worker". Although this has allowed him to continue to visit the site under Covid-19 restrictions, he delayed his first visit until 19th April 2020, when 3 transmitters had ceased to be in operation. The fact that the wind speeds look unrealistically slow between 12:10 and 15:00 UTC on that day is likely to be the result of LD carrying out the repairs. LD continued to visit the site at a reduced frequency during the next few months.

Prior to Covid-19 restrictions, LD had inspected the connectors for the power splitter feeding beam steering units 69, 70, 79, 80 on 7th February 2020. They appeared to have been chewed by rabbits.

The problem of a raised noise floor, which reduces useful altitude coverage, continued to be seen occasionally, e.g. on 5th, 6th, 12th, 27th, and 28th February 2020, on 5th March, and on 30th April. The raised noise floor seen on 20th/21st March 2020 seems to have been caused by the monitoring equipment that LD had installed in order to investigate the issue.

DAH had marked a couple of daily products files as containing suspect data owing to wind speeds within limited time/altitude regions that are much faster than adjacent times and altitudes. The issue was seen between 15:00 and 16:00 UTC and 15.8 - 17.0 km on 8th February 2020. There were a few instances above 15 km on 3rd April 2020.

There were a number of days on which the wind-profile data were contaminated over more-extended time/altitude regions. DAH refers to this an "sporadic E contamination" since it is consistent with radar returns from an altitude of around 105 km being range-aliased into the middle of the st-mode altitude range. However, he has no proof that sporadic E echoes are actually the cause of the problem. This issue was seen on 14th, 29th, 30th, and 31st May 2020, 1st June, 3rd, 12th, and 13th July.

5. Guest Instrument Report

GV and EGN reported that the Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) has generally been working well. There was a problem with the heating unit, which had to be replaced. The instrument has recently been dismantled so that the components can be sent back to the manufacturer for modifications. The entire receiver chain

will be upgraded. This will hopefully improve the altitude coverage and the reliability.

HMAR reported that data from the new Lufft laser ceilometer have been uploaded to the E-PROFILE programme since 24th February 2020. E-PROFILE's statistics show that the instrument provided 18% coverage in February 2020, 95% in April, and 100% in May and June. HMAR has updated the instrument's firmware, which did not produce any notable changes. Observations on clear sky days are needed in order to perform the calibration needed for quantifying aerosol concentrations. The instrument provides a measure of its window transmission, which primarily picks up rain events, but can also indicate an accumulation of dirt. HMAR is working on producing data files using the NCAS-AMOF standard. An order for a Cimel sun photometer for the CDAO was placed just before lockdown began and delivery is expected in 2021.

EGN reported that she had experienced difficulties in sending data from the RWP to E-PROFILE. DAH offered to help her since he has working scripts for sending MST Radar data. He noted that some of the E-PROFILE metadata associated with the MST radar data, which are added at the E-PROFILE hub rather than being included in the files that DAH sends, are slightly incorrect. This only became apparent when GAP drew his attention to the E-PROFILE data files that are being made available through CEDA. It also turns out that DAH is using a old method of sending data to E-PROFILE. The conversion from ASCII to BUFR format is carried out at the CDAO using a very old piece of software. The newer method is to send ASCII files to E-PROFILE with the conversion to BUFR taking place at their hub. DAH will need to make slight changes to the format of the ASCII files that he produces in order to move over to the newer system.

GAP reported that he is working with E-PROFILE to aggregate the ceilometer data sent to CEDA into daily netCDF files. Currently the data are available in a large number of shorter duration files. This is causing storage problems for CEDA.

GV reported that the Raman lidar is in working order. However, the Elight lidar has developed a problem. Since it will require two people to work in close proximity to investigate it further, it cannot be done under Covid-19 restrictions. Although the Lufft will become part of the CDAO suite of instruments, it makes sense for HMAR to look after it since he is already dealing with the same model of instrument. GAP reported that the Raman channel data from Met Office ceilometers will become available through CEDA from 23rd July 2020.

Finally, GV reported that the SAOZ instrument has essentially come to the end of its useful life. Although it used to be reliable, it could not be brought back into operation after its GPS module had to be replaced. The instrument is so old that the manufacturers don't know how to fix it.

6. Any Other Business

DAH reported that he will follow the lead of the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory regarding the easing of Covid-19 restrictions at the CDAO. He will need to update the Risk Assessment and Method Statements for STFC.

GV pointed out that it was important to replace the "chicken shacks" that house the primary power splitters within the MST radar antenna array. If water logging is thought to be the cause of the raised noise floor issue, the poor state of the current shacks is likely to be a contributory factor.

GV asked about the status of the Met Office's Radar Wind Profiler at Chilbolton, which has been gifted to NCAS. CJW reported that there had been an issue with the operating licence since the Met Office had a different method of covering their operational radars. He has spoken to Ofcom and is hoping that the RWP can be covered by a Trial and Innovation licence. EGN was concerned about whether the RWP

would still work when it is finally turned back on after a long period of down time.

DAH reported that an NCAS Radar Group has been set up with online meetings held every two weeks. He suggested that EGN might like to join the group.